

VALIDATION OF DIFFERENT IPM TECHNIQUES FOR SUSTAINABLE TEA PRODUCTION IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

The tea plant is subjected to the infestation of pests and diseases. To combat these maladies different control measures have been practiced in the tea garden of Bangladesh. Bangladesh Tea Research Institute has been successfully completed a sub-project entitled "Integrated pest management (IPM) approaches to major pests of tea for sustainable tea production" to minimize the use of synthetic pesticides by adopting IPM practices. BTRI has been developed IPM approaches for the control of four major pests of tea i.e. tea mosquito bug, red spider mite, thrips and looper caterpillar of tea in Bangladesh. Furthermore, a validation trial on different developed IPM techniques for sustainable tea production was done by Project Development Unit (PDU), Bangladesh Tea Board, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar during January to December 2022 at Baraooora Tea Estate, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar; Amtali Tea Estate, Bahubal, Habiganj and Six small tea gardens, Panchagarh Sadar, Panchagarh. The validation trials were set up following RCBD with five replications. Traditional/Conventional practice i.e. use of chemical pesticides to control pests in the tea garden was considered as control. Solar light trap and yellow sticky trap as IPM components were used for the controlling of thrips, jassid, white flies, and moths of caterpillar. Data were collected regularly at respective method and analyzed by means using SAS programme. The results showed that the solar-powered light trap and yellow sticky trap successfully trapped more thrips (112.32/trap) and (434.84/trap) followed by moths of looper caterpillar (34.64/trap) and (17.56/trap), respectively. Bio-control agent, *Bracon hebetor* as a larval parasitoid was very effective against looper caterpillar and significantly reduced the pest population. Result revealed that the parasitism of *B. hebetor* was found to be very effective, and the maximum mortality (98.42%) of looper caterpillars by the larval parasitoid of *B. hebetor* was found 21 days after release in the field condition. Therefore, the developed IPM techniques in tea such as solar power light traps, yellow sticky traps and *Bracon hebetor* have been validated and found to be satisfactory against different insect pests of tea. These would eventually eliminate the need for pesticides, lower production costs, and improve environmental safety.

Keywords: Tea, IPM, Solar light trap, Yellow sticky trap, Bio-control, *Bracon hebetor*, Looper caterpillar, Thrips, Sustainable tea production

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Introduction

Tea is a major cash crop as well as an important export commodity in Bangladesh. Tea is a long established plantation crop of enormous importance to Bangladesh, meeting almost the entire domestic demand for this cheapest health beverage. Now, there are 168 tea estates with about 66,000 hectares of tea plantations producing about 93.83 million kg of finished tea per annum with an average yield of about 1,700 kg per hectare in Bangladesh (BTB, 2022).

Tea plants are attacked by a variety of insects, mites, nematodes, fungal diseases, and weeds. A variety of pests attack tea plants, causing significant economic losses. Tea, as a long-lived woody perennial and monoculture, provides a stable microclimate and a steady source of food for the rapid growth of phytophagous organisms such as insects, mites, and eelworms. So far, 25 insects, 4 mites, and 12 nematode species have been identified in tea gardens of Bangladesh (Ahmed, 2005; Mamun, 2009). Among them, tea mosquito bug, red spider mites and termites are the major pests in mature tea plantation; while thrips, aphids, jassids, flushworms and nematodes are the major pests in nursery and young tea plantation. About 10-15% of its crop could be lost by various pests particularly insects, mites and nematodes. It may be extended to as high as 50% when pest attack/disease incidence is severe (Mamun, 2011).

Tea pests may be classified into three categories on the basis of the site of attack/infestation viz. *root pests* like nematode, termites, cockchafer grub; *stem pests* like red coffee borer, stem borer and *leaf pests* like tea mosquito bug, thrips, jassid, aphid, flushworm, looper caterpillar, leaf roller and all mite species (Mamun and Iyengar, 2010). Management of pests, diseases and weeds are an important operation in sustainable tea cultivation. To combat these problems different groups of chemical pesticides like organochlorine, organophosphate, pyrethroids, carbamates and some unclassified group have been used in the tea fields since 1960 (Mamun & Ahmed, 2011b; Ali et al., 2021). In this perspective, chemical control of pests is a dominating feature in Bangladesh tea (Alam, 1999). Chemical pesticides have been used for a long time, but have serious drawbacks, such as direct toxicity to beneficial insects, fishes and human being; pesticide induced resistance, health hazard and increased environmental, social costs and undesirable pesticide residue in made tea (Shrestha & Thapa, 2015). Therefore, managing these pest populations within economic threshold level is important for which application of pesticides becomes imperative in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) system. According to Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO, 1967), IPM is defined as “a pest management system, that, in the context of associated environment and population dynamics of the pest species, utilizes all suitable techniques and methods in as compatible a manner as possible and maintains pest populations at levels below those causing economic injury”.

A sub-project entitled “Integrated pest management (IPM) approaches to major pests of tea for sustainable tea production” under Competitive Research Grant (CRG) of NATP-2 of PIU, BARC was successfully done by Bangladesh Tea Research Institute to minimize the load of synthetic pesticides by adopting IPM practices during May 2017 to September 2018. BTRI has developed the IPM approaches for the control of four major pests of tea i.e. tea mosquito bug, red spider mite, thrips and looper caterpillar infesting tea in Bangladesh. Among the different components of IPM, different IPM techniques were validated during the validation period. The important components of IPM strategy i.e. Use of solar light traps, sticky traps and *Bracon hebetor* as larval parasitoid for major pests of tea which were validated in the experimental period that described below:

Solar light traps: Use of light trap is one of the important mechanical controls in IPM programme. Mechanical control means controlling pests and diseases with the help of mechanical measures. The behavior of certain species of insects being attracted to light could be advantageously used in their management. Light trap has often been used in the ecological studies of Lepidopteran insect pests in agroecosystems. Light trap is a cost effective and environment-friendly monitoring tool of Lepidopteran pests in tea plantations (Mamun & Ahmed, 2011a). Fluorescent light traps are useful in attracting the moths of caterpillars and other insects (Ahmed et al., 2010). They can be set up the seasons of moths' emergence. These traps are useful for monitoring the activity of the pests and as a means of control. Solar power light trap captured greater number of thrips and moths of looper caterpillar at different intervals (Mamun & Alam, 2018).

Sticky traps: In the tea ecosystem two types of traps, viz. Sticky traps (Adhesive traps) and Light traps may be used for monitoring and managing three upcoming major pests such as tea thrips, green hoppers and looper caterpillars. Yellow and blue sticky traps are also cost effective and eco-friendly monitoring tool for thrips, jassid, and Lepidopteran moths in tea plantations (Mamun et al., 2018). More number of thrips, jassids and moths of looper caterpillar were caught in the yellow sticky trap. However, the traps also captured a large number of non-target insects.

Bracon hebetor as larval parasitoid is under the biological control in IPM programme. It is one of the important components of IPM in many crops. Biological control involves the conservation, preservation and introduction of natural enemies like predators, parasitoids and pathogens for suppression of pests within tolerable levels. Biological control is one of the oldest pest management strategies that play a vital role in the control of many tea pests below economic injury level. The minor status of several pests such as aphids, scale insects, flushworms, leaf rollers and tea tortrix is due to the action of these natural enemies (Muraleedharan, 1992; Hazarika et al., 2001; Hazarika et al., 2009; (Kawai, 1997).

Within the framework of pest management, research has been conducted on cultural control, bio-control, resistant agrotypes, biopesticides, and any other IPM approaches against important insect pests of tea under CRG sub-project. So, attempts were made to validate developed IPM techniques for sustainable tea production in Bangladesh by Project Development Unit (PDU), Bangladesh Tea Board. The validation trial was conducted to evaluate the following IPM techniques viz.

- a. Use of yellow sticky traps against thrips, aphids, jassids, white flies.
- b. Use of light traps against thrips and moths of looper caterpillar
- c. Use of *Bracon hebetor* as larval parasitoid against looper caterpillar in tea.

Materials and Methods

A validation trial on different IPM techniques for sustainable tea production was done by Project Development Unit (PDU), Bangladesh Tea Board, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar during January to December 2022 at Baraora Tea Estate, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar; Amtali Tea Estate, Bahubal, Habiganj and Six small tea gardens, Panchagarh Sadar, Panchagarh. The validation trials were set up following RCBD with five replications. Two experimental plots have been set up at Amtoli Tea Estate, Bahubal, Habiganj in 2.47 acre area from where 1.23 acre was used for IPM plot and 1.23 acre was used for control plot. For the same reason, a different site at Baraora Tea Estate in Sreemangal, Moulvibazar and six farmers' plots in Panchagarh District were chosen. The IPM techniques i.e. yellow sticky traps @ 100 pieces per ha, solar light traps and *Bracon hebetor* were used in IPM research plot. The conventional method of tea pest control like spraying of chemical insecticide was applied in the control plot area. Data were collected regularly at respective method. The data on the number of infested shoots from both IPM research and control plots were analysed by two way ANOVA as well as the data on the number of healthy shoots from both of the plots were analysed by paired T test using SAS programme (Version 9.4). Means were separated with LSD test at 0.05 level of significance. On the other hand, the number of insect-pest captured from different traps were analysed by MS Excel.

Evaluation of solar light trap and yellow sticky traps against thrips and looper caterpillar in tea

An experiment was carried out to evaluate the solar light traps and sticky traps as mechanical control measures against thrips and looper caterpillar infesting tea at Baraora Tea Estate, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar; Amtali Tea Estate, Bahubal, Habiganj and Six small tea gardens, Panchagarh during January-December 2022. The experiment was set up following Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with five replications. Three treatments such as light trap (T₁), yellow sticky trap (T₂) and control (T₃) were considered in the study. Solar power light trap were used at night to attract the flying pests of tea i.e. thrips and moths of caterpillar. UV lights (220 V, 18 W, 5.2 nm; Philips) in the light traps were used in the experiment. The two light traps in the pair were placed approximately 600 m apart. Yellow sticky traps both sides coated with a thin film of a sticky adhesive were placed in the infested sections. The Yellow sticky card traps should be placed in the tea field 6 inch above the bush canopy (plucking table) at an angle 60° facing against wind by securing them on top of bamboo sticks. 10 sticky traps per 1000 m² were used in the study. A total of 100 traps are required per hectare. Post treatment observations on the attraction of pests were recorded at weekly interval up to 12 weeks.

Potential effects of Bracon hebetor as a bio-control agent for sustainable management of looper caterpillar

An experiment was carried out to determine the efficacy of bio-control agents i.e. *Bracon hebetor* as a larval parasitoid against Looper caterpillar infesting tea in field conditions. The trial was set up at Baraora Tea Estate, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar and Amtali Tea Estate, Bahubal, Habiganj. The adult female of *B. hebetor* @ 1 jar consisting around 800-1000 *Bracon* considered as treatment with three replications. The source of the bio-control agent is Ispahani Biotech Limited, Zareen Tea Estate, Srimangal, Moulvibazar. The potentiality of parasitoid on mortality of looper caterpillar was studied. Mortality data of looper caterpillar were collected at weekly interval.

Results and Discussion

Field evaluation of solar light trap and yellow sticky trap against thrips and looper caterpillar in tea

Result revealed that solar power light trap (T₁) captured greater number of thrips (112.32/trap) followed by white fly (64.42/trap) and moths (34.64/trap) of looper caterpillar, *B. suppressaria* at Sylhet region during January-December 2022 (Table 1). A few amounts of thrips, aphid, jassid, white flies, *Helopeltis* and termites are also captured in solar power light trap. In case of Panchagarh region, similar trend of captured of insect pests of tea was found (Table 2). [Sinu et al. \(2013\)](#) found the similar results. They found that male moths constitute more than 77% of the overall catches of looper caterpillar, *H. talaca*. Overall, our results highlight that light trap is an effective, bias-free monitoring tool of moth pests of tea, which also captures the variability due to habitat type. [Al Mamun et al. \(2020\)](#) reported that installing one light trap in an acre attracts at least more than 1000 adult pest for a day.

On the other hand, Yellow sticky traps are excellent tools for precision monitoring of thrips, jassids, white flies and leaf miners in tea. Yellow sticky traps (T₂) captured greater number of thrips (434.84/trap) followed by Jassid (252.36/trap) at Sylhet region during January-December 2022 (Table 1). However, the traps also captured a few number of non-target insects. In case of Panchagarh region, similar trend of captured of insect pests of tea was found (Table 2). [Prema et al. \(2018\)](#) found the similar results. They found that thrips catches on yellow sticky trap after 45, 60, 75 and 90 days of sowing of cotton were very high with 89.65, 120.00, 124.00, 91.90 numbers per trap, respectively. In another experiment, [Roy et al. \(2011\)](#) found that the field trials reflected that yellow sticky trap attracted more number of thrips compared to other colours. [Bian et al. \(2016\)](#) reported that lawn green and lime coloured traps are considered suitable to trap thrips in the tea plantations of southern China.

Table 1. Number of pest captured by the different IPM techniques evaluated at Sylhet region during January-December 2022.

Treatments	Number of pest captured by the IPM techniques evaluated at Sylhet region						
	Moth of looper caterpillar	Thrips	Aphid	Jassid	White fly	<i>Helopeltis</i>	Termite
T1 Solar light trap	34.64±0.84a	112.32±3.42b	26.48±0.54b	36.26±0.84b	64.42±0.60a	10.52±0.32b	4.84±0.12b
T2 Yellow sticky trap	17.56±0.68b	434.84±5.36a	48.18±0.82a	252.36±0.66a	42.60±0.76b	12.16±0.56a	8.08±0.34a

Means with the different letter are significantly different at $P>0.05$ using LSD.

Table 2. Number of pest captured by the different IPM techniques evaluated at Panchagarh region during January-December 2022.

Treatments	Number of pest captured by the IPM techniques evaluated at Panchagarh region						
	Moth of looper caterpillar	Thrips	Aphid	Jassid	White fly	<i>Helopeltis</i>	Termite
T1 Solar light trap	28.82±0.44a	86.34±1.38b	24.32±0.88b	30.66±0.47b	48.26±0.56a	8.24±0.44a	6.46±0.22a
T2 Yellow sticky trap	13.62±0.38b	294.32±2.36a	32.06±0.74a	164.42±0.54a	36.48±0.30b	6.10±0.28b	5.38±0.48b

Means with the different letter are significantly different at $P>0.05$ using LSD.

The proportion (%) of different insects captured on yellow sticky traps in the tea garden is presented in Figure 1. The study revealed that the yellow sticky traps captured the highest number of thrips (59.03%) followed by jassid (35.42%) and others insects (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Proportion (%) of different insect pests of tea trapped on yellow sticky traps in a tea garden at Sylhet region.

Field evaluation of Bracon hebetor as a bio-control agent for sustainable management of Looper caterpillar

Result revealed that parasitism of *B. hebetor* was found very effective and the maximum mortality (98.42%) of looper caterpillar by the larval parasitoid of *B. hebetor* was found at 21 days after release in the field condition (Fig.2). However, the *B. hebetor* may be used as a larval parasitoid for the control of looper caterpillar infesting tea as one of the strong IPM component.

Fig. 2. Mortality (%) of looper caterpillar parasitized by larval parasitoid *Bracon hebetor* at field condition

Comparison between combine effect of IPM techniques and conventional method on shoot infestation

Result revealed that there was no significant difference in the number of infested shoot by different insects between IPM plot and control plot (Table 3). It revealed that the control of insect-pest was similar in both plots. Therefore, these 2-3 IPM techniques such as use of yellow sticky traps, light traps and *B. hebetor* showed good performance rather than conventional control method in controlling insect-pest specially thrips, jassid and looper caterpillar. The results also indicated that the number of infested shoot in whole season by thrips, jassid, looper caterpillar, aphid, flushworm and leaf roller was very low as 8.10, 4.30, 6.80, 0.30, 0.90 and 0.20, respectively (Table 3). But the number of infested shoot by *Helopeltis* was very high (1059.30) in the whole cropping season. It suggested that the mentioned 2-3 IPM techniques performed excellent over controlling thrips, jassid, looper caterpillar, aphid, flushworm and leaf roller except *Helopeltis*.

Table 3. Effects of treatment (A) and insect (B) on the number of infested shoot in tea.

Treatment	Infested shoot
Treatment (A)	
IPM research plot	152.94a
Control plot	155.60a
Insect (B)	
Aphid	0.30b
Flushworm	0.90b
<i>Helopeltis</i>	1059.30a
Jassid	4.30b
Looper caterpillar	6.80b
Leaf roller	0.20b
Thrips	8.10b
Significance level	
Treatment	NS
Insect	**
Treatment*Insect	NS
Mean	154.27
CV (%)	67.65

Means with the same letter are not significantly different at $P>0.05$ using LSD.

In Amtoli Tea Estate, chemical pesticides have been used for a long time to control looper caterpillar, thrips and jassid but these chemical pesticides have had serious drawbacks, such as direct toxicity to beneficial insects, fishes and human being; increased environmental and social costs, and undesirable pesticide residue in made tea. Besides these, the usage of chemical pesticides in the tea garden required more labour and cost.

Cost involvement of the new system and compare with earlier system

The total cost for 123 decimal of validation trial plot was 30,010 taka. On the other hand, the total cost for the same area of control plot was 27,135 taka. Here, the cost was higher in the trial plot then the control plot as become of the tea production was higher in the trial plot, which resulted more labor cost and ultimately higher cost in trial plot.

Table 4. Comparison between IPM validation trial plot and control (Conventional) plot per hectare area at three locations during January-December 2022.

Location	IPM plot				Control plot			
	Yield	Total cost	Net Income	BCR	Yield	Total cost	Net Income	BCR
Amtali T.E.	2184	419328*	535342	1.28	1944	373248*	476514	1.28
Baraora T.E.	980	147000*	223440	1.52	1214	182100*	276792	1.52
Panchagarh	4932	207046	399600	1.93	4826	234810	390960	1.67

* Based on cost of production of the garden

Financial benefit earned from the technology and comparison with earlier similar technology

In the validation trial plot at Amtali T.E., the total made tea production in IPM plot was 2184 kg and total income was 535342 taka. In contrast with validation trial plot, the total made tea production in control plot was 1944 kg and total income was 373248 taka (Table 4). A total of 162094 taka (30.27%) more income achieved in validation trial plot rather than control plot. The benefit cost ratio (BCR) was also found 1.52

i.e. economically viable. More numbers of plucking resulted higher production in IPM trial plot. Plucking gap increased in control plot due to minimizing the residual effect of pesticides which results low tea production. Similar trends were found in case of Panchagarh. But a little difference was observed in the trial plot of Baraooora T.E. In addition, in the eco-friendly environment healthy tea production was possible, which is the most demandable issue in the today's world.

Interested number of people demanded to practice the technology

Field day program was done where tea garden managers were present and after visiting Amtoli tea estate's validation trial plot, many tea garden managers eagerly showed their interests to practice these IPM techniques in their tea garden in the next year. In the meantime, about 8 tea gardens in Moulvibazar area have been using yellow sticky trap as an IPM technology for controlling specially thrips and jassid in mature tea and nursery area.

Future plan to implement or continue the practice

The management of Amtoli Tea Estate already has made a plan to implement these IPM techniques in their tea estate for the area of 5 hectare of tea plantation. Project Development Unit of Bangladesh Tea Board usually monitors the development activities of 168 tea estates of Bangladesh yearly and suggests the garden authority to use IMP techniques in their tea gardens.

Conclusion and Recommendation

IPM strategy especially solar light trap, yellow trap and bio-control agent i.e. *Bracon hebetor* parasitoid against pests of tea has been successfully evaluated, validated and implemented in tea gardens. Solar power light traps and yellow sticky traps as mechanical control measures have been validated and found to be very effective against moths of looper caterpillar and thrips. This sticky traps worked best for sucking pests and helps in trapping the population of thrips, jassids, white flies and adults of tea mosquito bugs. They are environment-friendly and cost-effective. Bio-control agent, *B. hebetor* as larval parasitoid against looper caterpillar has been validated and found to be satisfactory to control of the larvae of looper caterpillar. These IPM techniques were found very effective for the control of thrips and looper caterpillar which significantly reduced the risk of pesticide and chemical uses on tea, besides improving quality, health and welfare of the environment. IPM promotes sustainable bio-based pest management alternatives in pest management programme in the tea garden. IPM protects non-target species through reduced impact of pest management activities. It reduces or eliminates issues related to pesticide residue in made tea. It also decreases worker, tenant and public exposure to pesticides and leads to safe livelihoods. IPM maintains or increases the cost-effectiveness of a pest management programme. Moreover, if made tea produced from IPM treated field is to be sold in the auction separately, then the planters/managers/small growers would get better price and users would be eagerly interested to use IPM techniques in tea plantation in Bangladesh.

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References

- Ahmed, M. (2005). *Tea Pest Management*. Evergreen Printing and Packaging. Dhaka. 118p.
- Ahmed, M., Mamun, M. S. A., & Paul, S. K. (2010). Looper caterpillar-a threat to tea and its management. BTRI Circular no. 132, Bangladesh Tea Research Institute, Srimangal, Moulvibazar. pp. 1-7.
- Al Mamun, M. R., Keya, A. C., & Alim, M. S. (2020). Integrated pest management (IPM) through solar light trap in tea (*Camellia sinensis*) garden. In Proceedings of the conference on International conference on sustainable agriculture and rural development: Road to SDGs, Sylhet Agricultural University, Sylhet-3100, Bangladesh.

- Alam, A. F. M. B. (1999). Profile of tea industry in Bangladesh. In N. K. Jain (Ed.), *Global Advances in Tea Science*. Aravali Book International (P) Ltd. New Delhi-110020. 370p.
- Ali, M., Mamun, M. S. A., Paul, S. K. and Alam, M. J. (2021). Approved insecticides, miticides and nematocides for tea (Revised & Updated). BTRI Circular no. 148, Bangladesh Tea Research Institute, Srimangal, Moulvibazar. 44p.
- Bian, L., Yang, P. X., Yao, Y. J., Luo, Z. X., Cai, X. M., Chen, Z. M. (2016). Effect of trap color, height, and orientation on the capture of yellow and stick tea thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and non-target insects in tea gardens. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 109(3), 1241-1248. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/tow007>
- BTB. (2022). Statistical Bulletin of Bangladesh Tea Board for the month of December 2022. Bangladesh Tea Board, Nasirabad, Chittagong. p.1.
- FAO. (1967). Report of the First Session of the FAO Panel of Experts on Integrated Pest Control. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Rome, Italy.
- Hazarika, L. K., Bhuyan, M. & Hazarika, B N. (2009). Insect pests of tea and their management. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 54, 267-284. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ento.53.103106.093359>
- Hazarika, L. K., Puzari, K. C., & Wahab, S. (2001). Biological control of tea pests (pp. 159-180), In R. K. Upadhyay, K. G. Mukerji, B. P. Chamola (eds). *Biocontrol potential and its exploitation in sustainable agriculture*. Springer, Boston, MA, USA. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-1377-3_11
- Kawai, A. (1997). Prospect for integrated pest management in tea cultivation in Japan. *Japan Agricultural Research Quarterly*, 31, 213-217.
- Mamun, M. S. A. (2011). Integrated approaches to tea pest management in south India: A way of sustainable tea cultivation. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing GmbH & Co. KG DudweilerLandstr. 99, 66123 Saarbrücken, Germany. 68p. ISBN: 978-3-8465-5088-5.
- Mamun, M. S. A. (2019). Tea production in Bangladesh: from bush to mug (pp. 441-505), In M. Hasanuzzaman (eds). *Agronomic Crops*. Volume 1, Chapter 21, Springer, Singapore. ISBN: 978-981-32-9150-8. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-32-9151-5_21
- Mamun, M. S. A., & Ahmed, M. (2011a). Integrated pest management in tea: prospects and future strategies in Bangladesh. *Journal of Plant Protection Sciences*, 3(2), 1-13.
- Mamun, M. S. A., & Ahmed, M. (2011b). Prospect of indigenous plant extracts in tea pest management. *International Journal of Agricultural Research, Innovation and Technology*, 1(1-2), 16-23. <https://doi.org/10.3329/ijarit.v1i1-2.13924>
- Mamun, M. S. A., & Alam, M. J. (2018). Integrated Pest Management (IPM) approaches to major pests of tea for sustainable tea production. *A report of Competitive Research Grant under National Agricultural Technology Program-Phase II Project (NATP-2)*, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council (BARC), Farmgate, Dhaka. 53p.
- Mamun, M. S. A., & Iyengar, A. V. K. (2010). Integrated approaches to tea pest management in south India. *International Journal of Sustainable Agricultural Technology*, 6(4), 27-33.
- Mamun, M. S. A., Alam, M. J., & Ali, M. (2018). Integrated pest management (IPM) approaches to major pests of tea for sustainable tea production. A Booklet of IPM project, Bangladesh Tea Research Institute, Srimangal, Moulvibazar. pp. 1-8.
- Muraleedharan, N. (1992). Pest control in Asia (pp. 375-412). In K. C. Willson, M. N. Clifford (eds), *Tea*. Springer, Dordrecht, Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-011-2326-6_12
- Prema, M. S., Ganapathy, N., Renukadevi, P., Mohankumar, S., & Kennedy, J. S. (2018). Coloured sticky traps to monitor thrips population in cotton. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies*, 6(2), 948-952.
- Roy, S., Gurusubramanian, G., & Nachimuthu, S. K. (2011). Neem based integrated approaches for the management of tea thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood (Thripidae: Thysanoptera) in tea. *Proceedings of Zoological Society*, 64(2), 72-77. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12595-011-0015-y>
- Shrestha, G., & Thapa, R. B. (2015). Tea pests and pesticide problems and integrated management. *Journal of Agriculture and Environment*, 16, 188-200. <https://doi.org/10.3126/aej.v16i0.19852>
- Sinu, P. A., Mandal, P., Banerjee, D., Mallick, S., Talukdar, T., & Pathak, S. K. (2013). Moth pests collected in light traps of tea plantations in North East India: species composition, seasonality and effect of habitat type. *Current Science*, 104(5), 646-651.

Appendix I. Some pictorials of validation trial on Solar light trap as IPM technique at different locations.

Appendix II. Some pictorials of validation trial on Yellow sticky trap as IPM technique at different locations.

